

AMIRÈS

QUANTUM TECHNOLOGIES Investment Report

2024

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Introduction and foreword

The 2024 Quantum Technologies Investment Report offers an in-depth look at the key funding trends within the quantum technologies sector.

As quantum technologies gain traction and expand into various practical applications, the startup ecosystem within the field continues to grow. The immense potential of these technologies has made them an increasingly appealing investment opportunity, as reflected in the consistent flow of funding supporting such companies over time.

This report provides valuable insights into the investment landscape, examining trends across various time frames, regions, and product focuses. It serves as a guide for investors seeking to make informed decisions, addressing questions like: What areas are attracting investment? What is the typical funding size for emerging companies? How does Europe measure up against other regions worldwide?

The report compiles data gathered in 2024.

Our goal is to provide investors with a comprehensive market overview to encourage greater involvement in the quantum sector. With Europe poised to lead in these technologies, it is crucial to ensure that investments are both informed and effective. Additionally, the insights shared in this report can serve as a valuable resource for young companies seeking both private and public funding.

Let's dive into the quantum technology investment landscape together.

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Methodology

This report relies on a comprehensive collection of information primarily sourced from publicly available online platforms. To ensure validity and accuracy, data has been cross-referenced across multiple reputable sources.

Key platforms used in this research include The Quantum Insider, Crunchbase, Infinity QD, and Global Quantum Intelligence, among others, which have provided valuable insights into the quantum technology landscape. In instances where specific data was not publicly accessible, our team utilized subscription-based services, such as AMIPLEXUS, to access internal databases.

It is important to note that this research focuses exclusively on venture capital funding. Internal investments by large tech companies, funding from publicly listed companies via the stock exchange, and non-dilutive public funding have not been considered in the analysis.

To simplify comparisons, deals conducted in euros were converted to US dollars using the exchange rate on the date the deal was finalized. This ensures consistency across the financial data presented.

All numerical data and graphical representations in this report were generated internally by our team of experts. These insights are drawn from the collective expertise of professionals engaged in quantum investment support activities.

Most graphs in the report highlight data on the number and value of investments made in 2024. The "number of investments" refers to the count of deals, while the "amount" reflects the financial value of those deals. It is worth noting that certain outlier multi-million-dollar deals, such as those involving SandboxAQ or PsiQuantum, have significantly influenced the charts and overall trends.

While every effort was made to ensure completeness, some minor gaps in information may exist due to the reliance on publicly available sources. However, these omissions are unlikely to impact the overall findings and conclusions of this report.

Key takeaways

The analysis of quantum startups that secured private investment in 2024 revealed crucial insights and trends, offering a clearer understanding of the industry's future trajectory. Here are some of the key findings.

- 1.** Half of global quantum investments were directed towards **European startups**, with Europe standing out for its strong presence of startups in the critical **seed** and **Series A** stages.
- 2.** **North America** saw a sharp **rise in investments** and more than **doubled the amounts** compared to 2023, while **Europe** maintained steady activity but saw a **14% decline** in total investment amount.
- 3.** In terms of technology, the highest private capital is directed towards **photonics**, **superconducting**, and **neutral atoms**-based qubits.
- 4.** **Quantum computing** attracts the highest number of private deals, followed closely by **quantum communication**, while **quantum sensing** has also seen a notable increase in investments in 2024.
- 5.** Nearly half of the deals were concentrated in **hardware**-focused companies, while the largest investment amounts are directed towards **software** and **hardware-software** combined companies.

Geography and origin

Global investment leaders

1/2 of global quantum investment deals in 2024 were made in European startups.

INVESTMENTS IN QUANTUM TECHNOLOGIES

NUMBER BY THE STARTUP'S LOCATION

2024

Key insights

- Europe and North America continue to lead in the field, with **North America** significantly **increasing its number of deals** and more than **doubling the amounts** compared to 2023.
- In contrast, **Europe** maintained its activity level, though the total amount invested saw a **14% decline**.

INVESTMENTS IN QUANTUM TECHNOLOGIES

AMOUNT BY THE STARTUP'S LOCATION (\$MLN)

2023 & 2024

The logos represent the companies that have received the most significant investments in 2023 and 2024.

Expert says...

While North America's quantum investments surged ahead in 2024, Europe demonstrated its enduring strength in innovation. A standout success is Riverlane, the Cambridge-based startup advancing quantum operating systems, which secured a significant funding round. This achievement underscores Europe's vital role in driving quantum technology forward, even as North America doubles down on its investment commitments.

Robert Harrison, Sonnenberg Harrison

Geography and origin

European startups' investment sources

WHO'S INVESTING IN EUROPEAN QUANTUM STARTUPS? BY INVESTOR'S ORIGIN 2024

Key insights

- Europe continues to predominantly support its own companies.
- Compared to 2023, when American investors primarily participated in more mature rounds, in 2024 they also actively invested in **Seed**-stage startups.

INVESTORS IN QUANTUM TECHNOLOGIES BY NUMBER OF INVESTMENTS AS LEAD INVESTORS GLOBALLY JULY 2022 - DECEMBER 2024

Expert says...

In 2023, Europe has shown resilience in quantum investments, with a lot of European top venture firms that kept on investing in the sector while investments made by US funds were down significantly. While European funds total investment amounts may be smaller than those of their American counterparts, their strong presence and leadership in funding rounds underscore Europe's significant role in advancing quantum technologies.

Olivier Tonneau, Quantonation

Geography and origin

European quantum startup leaders

NUMBER OF INVESTMENTS RECEIVED
BY EUROPEAN QUANTUM STARTUPS
BY COUNTRY OF ORIGIN

2024

The logos represent the companies that have received the most significant investments in 2024.

Expert says...

Europe boasts a vibrant and geographically diverse quantum ecosystem, supported by robust governmental initiatives that nurture innovation, facilitate collaboration, and drive the growth of cutting-edge technologies in the field.

Thierry Botter, European Quantum Industry Consortium

In our **2023** report, we highlighted **European startups** that secured **pre-seed or seed funding**, showcasing emerging players in the quantum technology landscape.

This year, we revisit one of those **standout startups** from 2023, now achieving a **significant milestone** in 2024 through **strategic collaborations within the quantum ecosystem**. Their progress exemplifies how partnerships and shared expertise can accelerate innovation, turning early-stage potential into tangible breakthroughs that drive the industry forward.

In December 2023, **Kipu Quantum** raised €10.5M in seed funding from HV Capital and DeepTech & Climate Fonds to advance hardware-specific quantum algorithms. In July 2024, the company acquired PlanQK, a German quantum computing platform, to speed up the commercialization of its quantum solutions.

Geography and origin

European companies to watch

These early-stage quantum technology companies in Europe have received seed funding in 2024.

Each one of them bringing unique solutions to different industries. What unites these companies, however, is their shared focus on tackling problems across multiple sectors and integrating hardware and software to address some of the most complex challenges in quantum computing, photonics, cryogenics, and beyond.

EUROPEAN QUANTUM COMPANIES THAT RECEIVED SEED INVESTMENT

2024

Let's monitor their progress in translating their funding into products - these are the players of the European future of quantum technologies!

Geography and origin

Investment trends: in Europe vs global

52 private investment deals in quantum startups were recorded globally in 2024, slightly up from 50 in 2023.

This growth in deal activity reflects a broader trend: despite a decline in private venture capital flow into quantum startups in 2023, **the global appetite for investing in the field continues to expand in 2024**. The trend is particularly evident in America, where interest and activity remain strong, while Europe has seen comparatively less enthusiasm from investors and smaller total amounts this year.

**TOTAL AMOUNT OF INVESTMENTS
IN QUANTUM STARTUPS IN EUROPE AND GLOBALLY (\$MLN)**
2023 & 2024

The peaks in global investments were driven by **SandboxAQ's \$500M deal in Q1 2023** and **PsiQuantum's \$617M deal in Q2 2024**, highlighting their outsized impact. In contrast, Europe maintained a steadier trajectory, with a focus on smaller, incremental funding rounds.

Deal type

Participation in public funding programmes

Horizon Europe (2021-2027) is one of the EU's main research and innovation funding program, aiming to enhance Europe's global competitiveness by supporting various research projects, including those in the quantum sector.

Given the importance of this program, we focused our analysis on companies that secured **private funding** in 2024 and also received **public support** through Horizon Europe (HEU). While our analysis highlights HEU, it's worth noting that these companies may also benefit from other public funding sources.

Key insights

- Over half of **EU based quantum startups** with private funding in 2024 also **received public funding** from **Horizon Europe**.
- HEU funds **early-stage research and feasibility**, while private funding focuses on **scaling and commercialization**, explaining the larger private investment amounts. (see chart below)

AMOUNT OF INVESTMENTS MADE IN QUANTUM STARTUPS BY PUBLIC (HORIZON EUROPE 2021-2027) AND PRIVATE FUNDING (2024) (\$MLN)

Expert says...

The mix of public and private funding is crucial for advancing quantum technology. Public grants, including those from programs like Horizon Europe, play a pivotal role in supporting early-stage research and foundational advancements, while private capital drives scalability and commercialization. This balance fosters R&D, boosts credibility, and ensures financial stability. Programs like Horizon Europe and other public funding sources are essential for bridging the funding gap, addressing differing risk appetites, and maintaining Europe's global competitiveness in this strategic field.

Mika Prunnila, VTT

Deal type

Investments by investment series

NUMBER OF INVESTMENTS MADE IN QUANTUM STARTUPS GLOBALLY BY FUNDING ROUNDS

2024

Key insights

- **More than 80%** of the reported total investments in 2024 were made through **Seed** and **A** rounds.
- Investments in **Pre-seed** startups **decreased** by nearly **80%**, while those in **Series B** dropped by **46%**.

The graph includes both **main** and **extension** rounds for each funding stage.

American company SandboxAQ, which previously closed a \$500 million deal in early 2023, secured another significant \$300 million round in late 2024. However, as the details of this year's round are undisclosed, it's not included in this chart.

AMOUNT OF INVESTMENTS MADE IN QUANTUM STARTUPS GLOBALLY BY FUNDING ROUNDS (\$MLN)

2024

Expert says...

In 2024, the absence of Series D investments contrasted with the significant impact of early Series E rounds from American startups Quantinuum and PsiQuantum, which dominated total funding. Despite this, Series A rounds ranked second, reflecting strong momentum in early-stage activity. The drop in pre-seed investments may stem from a growing preference for Seed and Series A stages, offering better risk-return balance, and some pre-seed startups choosing to remain in stealth mode to refine their models before seeking visibility.

Audrey Durand, Institut d'Optique

Product type

Technology domain

INVESTMENTS IN QUANTUM TECHNOLOGIES AMOUNT BY TECHNOLOGY DOMAIN (\$MLN)

2023 & 2024

Key insights

- In 2024, investment in **Quantum Computing**-focused companies saw a significant surge, with **funding amounts doubling** compared to 2023, despite the **number of deals dropping** by over 10%.
- **Quantum Communication**-focused companies maintained a consistent funding level, but the **number of deals increased by 5%**, reflecting steady growth in interest.
- **Quantum Sensing** companies saw their share of **total deals grow from 3% to 10%**, accompanied by a **doubling in total investment** this year.

INVESTMENTS IN QUANTUM TECHNOLOGIES NUMBER BY TECHNOLOGY DOMAIN

2024

Expert says...

Quantum sensing startups are attracting more investor interest, driven by both an increase in the number of startups and growing recognition of the sector's commercial potential. With applications across industries like healthcare and defense, quantum sensing offers unique advantages and is closer to practical use than quantum computing, making it highly appealing to investors seeking shorter-term returns.

Gabriele Bulgarini, TNO

Product type

Quantum computing technologies

NUMBER OF INVESTMENTS IN QUANTUM STARTUPS
BY THEIR HARDWARE'S QUBIT MODALITY

2024

Key insights

- **Photonics, superconducting** and **neutral atoms** qubit modalities continue to maintain their positions as the **foremost approaches in quantum computing hardware**.
- In 2024, no investments were recorded in companies focused solely on NV centers in diamond, cavity QED, or topological qubits, suggesting a shift in quantum funding priorities.

AMOUNT OF INVESTMENTS IN QUANTUM STARTUPS
BY THEIR HARDWARE'S QUBIT MODALITY (\$MLN)

2024

Expert says...

The investment landscape for quantum hardware approaches in 2024 was shaped by two standout deals: PsiQuantum's \$617M investment in Photonics and Quantinuum's \$300M funding in Trapped ions. These outliers created a dramatic disparity in funding distribution across modalities, underscoring the significant influence of individual high-value deals. Without these, the differences in investment amounts between specific approaches would have been far less pronounced.

Roman Pašek, AMIRES

Product type

Category - hardware, software or both?

Key insights

- Unlike in 2023, when software-focused companies attracted the most investment, **in 2024, nearly half of the deals are in hardware-focused companies.**
- The growing number of investments in hardware-software companies since 2023 reflects a **rising demand for integrated solutions.**

We analyzed investment patterns from **July 2022 to December 2024**, revealing an interesting contrast in funding distribution among hardware-focused, software-focused, and combined hardware-software companies.

NUMBER AND AMOUNT OF INVESTMENTS BY PRODUCT TYPE (HARDWARE/SOFTWARE)

JULY 2022 - DECEMBER 2024

Expert says...

Hardware-focused companies, despite comprising a larger percentage of the sector, have attracted less funding. In contrast, software-centric firms, though fewer in number, have secured more substantial investments. Notably, companies integrating both hardware and software, representing the smallest segment, have garnered the highest investment amounts. This pattern underscores a growing recognition of the value in comprehensive quantum solutions that bridge hardware and software capabilities.

Anca Albu, QAI Ventures

Investor profiles

One of our goals is to build relationships with investors and businesses to direct funding into promising companies best suit the investor profiles. By understanding the unique perspectives and criteria of each investor, we aim to facilitate meaningful partnerships that align with their objectives and contribute to the advancement of quantum companies.

To be featured in the forthcoming edition of the report, kindly reach out to us with your investment focus and relevant information.

The investors mentioned herein have not taken part in the creation or approval of the report's content. Therefore, they are not held responsible for the accuracy of the information presented.

Eureka! Ventures

www.eurekaventure.it

HTGF

www.htgf.de

LiFTT

<https://www.liftt.com/en>

PhotonVentures

www.photonventures.vc

QAI Ventures

<https://qai-ventures.com/>

Quantonation

www.quantonation.com

Redstone

www.redstone.vc

Tensor Ventures

www.tensor.ventures

Verve Ventures

www.verve.vc

Vigo Ventures

www.vigo.ventures

Voima Ventures

www.voimaventures.com

Investor profiles

INVESTOR PROFILE

TECHNOLOGY FOCUS

- Deep tech investments in energy, health and wellness, mobility and environment
- With innovation underpinned by advanced materials

BASE

- Pre-revenue
- Revenue

LOCATION

Italy, Europe

LOOKING FOR

- Dedicated and bold teams capable of bringing disruptive advanced materials innovations to global markets

SERIES

- Pre-seed
- Seed
- Round A
- Round B

AMOUNT

EUR 500K – 3 MLN

WEBSITE

www.eurekaventure.it

QU-TEST & QU-PILOT

INVESTOR PROFILE

TECHNOLOGY FOCUS

- Sector agnostic

BASE

- Pre-revenue
- Revenue

LOCATION

Germany, Europe

LOOKING FOR

- Strongly differentiated Tech-Start-Ups
- Scientific Breakthroughs
- Product-Market-Fit

AMOUNT

EUR 500K – 1 MLN

WEBSITE

www.htgf.de

QU-TEST & QU-PILOT

Investor profiles

INVESTOR PROFILE

TECHNOLOGY FOCUS

- Quantum Technologies
- AI Infrastructure
- Future of Computing
- SpaceTech
- Biotech
- MedTech
- Energy & ClimaTech
- Photonics
- New Materials
- Robotics

BASE

- Pre-revenue
- Revenue

LOCATION

Europe, USA, Global

LOOKING FOR

- Team with scientific know-how
- Competitive and unique IPs
- Disruptive and enabling technology

WEBSITE

www.liftt.com

SERIES

- Pre-seed
- Seed
- Round A
- Round B

AMOUNT

EUR 500K – 3 MLN

INVESTOR PROFILE

TECHNOLOGY FOCUS

- Integrated photonics solutions including quantum applications communication
- Data/Telecom, Medical/Healthcare, Engineering & Transport, Food & Agriculture

BASE

- Pre-revenue
- Revenue

LOCATION

Europe

LOOKING FOR

- Applications with integrated photonics technology
- MVP ready
- Global market potential
- Complementary team

WEBSITE

www.photonventures.vc

SERIES

- Seed
- Round A

AMOUNT

EUR 500K – 5 MLN

Investor profiles

INVESTOR PROFILE

TECHNOLOGY FOCUS

- Advanced computing, with quantum technology and/ or advanced AI at the forefront

BASE

- Pre-revenue
- Revenue

LOCATION

Global

SERIES

- Pre-seed
- Seed
- Round A
- Round B
- Round C

LOOKING FOR

- Growing, revenue-generating startups in the field of advanced computing

AMOUNT

EUR 200K – 10 MLN

WEBSITE

www.qai-ventures.com

INVESTOR PROFILE

TECHNOLOGY FOCUS

- Quantum Technologies
- Deep Physics

BASE

- Pre-revenue
- Revenue

LOCATION

Global

SERIES

- Pre-seed
- Seed
- Round A
- Round B

LOOKING FOR

- Early stage companies out of the best physics labs

AMOUNT

EUR 500K – 1.5 MLN

WEBSITE

www.quantonation.com

Investor profiles

INVESTOR PROFILE

REDSTONE

TECHNOLOGY FOCUS

- Artificial Intelligence
- Connectivity
- Future of Compute, Quantum Computing
- Photonics & Electronics
- Robotics

BASE

- Pre-revenue
- Revenue

LOCATION

Europe, Global

SERIES

- Seed
- Round A

LOOKING FOR

- Technically excellent and balanced team
- Unique product
- Route to commercialization

AMOUNT

EUR 500K – 2 MLN

WEBSITE

www.redstone.vc

QU-TEST & QU-PILOT

INVESTOR PROFILE

**[] tensor
ventures**

TECHNOLOGY FOCUS

- Quantum Technologies
- Digital AI
- Computational Biotech
- Cybersecurity
- Future of Computing
- Spacetech
- Energy&Climate Tech
- Advanced Physics

BASE

- Pre-revenue
- Revenue

LOCATION

Europe, Global

SERIES

- Pre-seed
- Seed

LOOKING FOR

- Product market fit
- Team over maturity
- Uniqueness of the solution

AMOUNT

EUR 500K – 1.5 MLN

WEBSITE

www.tensor-ventures

QU-TEST & QU-PILOT

Investor profiles

INVESTOR PROFILE

VERVE
VENTURES

TECHNOLOGY FOCUS

- Energy & Resources
- Future of Computing
- Health & Bio

BASE

- Pre-revenue
- Revenue

LOCATION

Switzerland, Europe

SERIES

- Pre-seed
- Seed
- Round A

LOOKING FOR

- Strong value proposition
- Excellent team with strong scientific and commercial capabilities

AMOUNT

EUR 500K – 3 MLN

WEBSITE

www.verve.vc

INVESTOR PROFILE

VIGO
VENTURES

TECHNOLOGY FOCUS

- Photonics
- Semiconductors
- Quantum Technologies

BASE

- Pre-revenue
- Revenue

LOCATION

Europe, USA, Canada

SERIES

- Pre-seed
- Seed

LOOKING FOR

- First VC round
- Photonics (HW or HW+SW)
- IP driven
- TRL 4/5

AMOUNT

Deal size with follow-on:
EUR 200K - 1.5 MLN
Growth follow-on PE
partner possibility:
up to EUR 15 MLN

WEBSITE

www.vigo.ventures

Investor profiles

Where does it lead us?

With these findings in hand, we are determined to strengthen and simplify the European quantum landscape. Our objective is to push the industry forward through a targeted plan structured around three critical steps:

01

Attract and connect

Attract and unite investors with publicly funded resources, forging connections between the worlds of public and private funding, recognizing their potential to complement each other.

02

Introduce

Introduce investor profiles to highlight businesses aligned with their specific focus and objectives. If you're an investor eager to connect with promising quantum startups and would like to be featured in our LinkedIn or upcoming report, please reach out to us.

03

Promote

Promote the Qu-Test and Qu-Pilot projects, tailored to support private companies in advancing quantum technologies.

Be sure to follow our [website](#) and [LinkedIn](#) to stay informed about the latest news, and success stories from these projects.

- ✉ info@qu-test.eu
- ✉ info@qu-pilot.eu
- 🌐 www.qu-pilot.eu
- 🌐 www.qu-test.eu
- 🌐 [QU-TEST & QU-PILOT](#)

About Qu-Test and Qu-Pilot Projects

QU- TEST

The Qu-Test project aims to create a network of quantum technology testing and experimentation service providers across Europe. The project aims to upgrade, upscale and integrate the testing and experimentation infrastructures and associated processes for quantum technologies. The objective is to create open-access distributed testing and experimentation infrastructure to make quantum technology facilities and associated services available to clients in all 27 EU countries. The target is to validate the relevance of the testbed service offering and the robustness of the Single-Entry-Point processes through the implementation of industrial use cases.

1st Project kick-off in April 2023

Budget: 19 M€
Duration: 3.5 years
Coordinator: TNO (NL)

Project Coordinator
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QU- PILOT

The Qu-Pilot project aims to leverage existing piloting infrastructure across Europe to support the growing European quantum technology industry. The project seeks to establish RTO-driven pilot facilities that will be well-networked and interact with each other. The end goal is to accelerate the time-to-market of European industrial innovation in quantum technology and establish a trusted supply chain. Besides, Qu-Pilot envisions developing practical strategies in synergy with European academic and industrial players to provide the quantum ecosystem with a 'one-stop-shop' offering unique facilities, competencies and know-how available in Europe.

1st Project kick-off in April 2023

Budget: 19 M€
Duration: 3.5 years
Coordinator: VTT (FI)

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AMIRES, The Business Innovation Management Institute (ABIMI)

ABIMI specializes in the management of national and international research, development, and innovation projects, focusing on new materials, production processes, information technologies, healthcare, energy, and environmental sustainability. We offer consulting services to enhance the quality of life and competitiveness across Europe. We promote funding opportunities, disseminate information, organize events, and publish activities related to our core areas of expertise. Additionally, we offer storage and processing of data from research projects, along with research and development of innovative data acquisition, processing, and visualization methods to further improve quality of life and competitiveness in our regions of operation.

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